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FUNCTIONAL SYSTEM APPROACH TO THE CRITICAL PATIENT

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Annotation: The proposed scientific article pursues the main goal – to combine the methodology of anesthesiology, resuscitation and intensive care on a functional rather than on an organ-physiological syndromic basis. The organ-physiological approach involves the treatment of pneumonia, myocardial infarction, stroke, etc. With a functional systemic approach, the organ is, in fact, an argument and is in general connection with the whole organism. The general connection in philosophical language sounds like determinism, i.e. everything that surrounds a person, including healing, obeys the laws of determinism. Therefore, intensive therapy of a patient in a critical condition on the basis of a functional systemic approach will make it possible to more accurately formulate the subject and methods of anesthesiology, resuscitation and intensive care from the position of philosophical understanding of the interaction of the integrity of human life with the phenomenon of death, and methodologically substantiate the identification of

typical pathological processes both in sanogenesis and in thanatogenesis, taking into account their interaction.

Keywords: functional systems approach, critical condition

«The priority is not to reveal the cause of death, but find out why life has stopped» [1].

When did the idea of world integrity appear? Presumably, when it was for the first time said, «In the beginning was the Word, and the Word was with God, and the Word was God» [2]. With consciousness development and experience accumulation people felt the need for realization of integrity along with its interaction with multiple parts in cognitive and practical activity. There appeared, at first glance, the controversy of the whole and the particular, that has given rise to a long debate in science, research and education. The first position asserted a holistic phenomenological method in research and educational work. The other, on the contrary, gave priority to the analytical and empirical approach. However, a marginal approach to the problem often accompanies its crisis development, which contradicts the evolution of biomedical systems.

Systematic functional approach is a nature-founded bridge between analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, and, in general, between the formal and dialectical categories, and its implementation seems to be started with the interaction and formation of the final beneficial result, that should be reflected in the terms of present time reality and socio-economic demand.

At the beginning of XX century there was proposed the concept of "system" [3-5]. With the help of a new mechanism there appeared an opportunity to consider interaction of the whole and the particular, where the contradictions had to give way to interaction, or even cooperation and synergy, according to the evolution of the nature of the whole, especially in medical and biological systems.

The term "system" has a long history, and there is hardly a human activity, where it is not used. Primarily, the term appeared in the technical, industrial and socio-political systems. The common characteristic feature of these systems is determinacy in obtaining the final positive result. But in biomedical systems the determinacy principle gave way to the probability of obtaining the final expedient result. The nature of the feedback changed, and there appeared reciprocal aspect in the causal relationships of and controlling and controlled mechanisms in self-managed systems, that determined the complexity and unpredictability of the biological systems behavior. On the ground of the aforesaid there evolved different concepts of functional systematic approach in different areas of social and economic activity: organ-physiological hierarchical, cybernetics and mathematical, etc.

The special interest arises in the application of functional systematic approach to biological systems where cybernetic and mathematical abstraction gives way to dialectical comprehension [6], especially in the interaction of conflicting identities, with the acute need to solve the situation urgently. Characteristic feature of a clinical resuscitation situation is self-organization and self-regulation of the multiple variable functions and their interaction in homeokinesis. At the same time there is a real need to evaluate not only cooperation and synergy of homeokinesis multiple indices, but also their hierarchical regulation within the whole organism, the problem, which was solved in our domestic medicine with the use of clinical thinking. However, in imitation or simulation of reality, when the trainee does not deal with reality, but only with its shadow, the very essence of clinical training changes so that healing becomes virtual and thus virtually successful.

Medical systems has long been considered without their peculiarities that, as shown by further studies, is significantly altering the functional systematic approach. The latter should clarify the complex mechanisms of interaction for various forms of life and its reverse side – death, explaining the empirical material that was not even presupposed while the patient observation. Thus, there arose a difficult situation seemingly without a way out, that caused a cool attitude to the functional systematic approach in medicine and education, and it is associated with a number of diverse reasons:

- excessive theorizing in functional systematic approach, starting with the very definition of "system";
- neglect of functional systematic approach peculiarities in biomedical systems, and underestimation of probability and character of interaction for multiple variable functions;
- excessive importance of mathematical abstraction in functional system modeling;
- probability of the result expediency and utility in the system-forming factor and underestimation of its character in the interaction with integral afferent signal;
- attempt to develop the one-way concept of functional system, while there probably takes place a combinative concept, considering the principles of organ-physiological, hierarchical and mathematical models of functional systems.

It is the combinative concept that suits the holistic approach, where may be found the harmony and measure of the cause and effect interaction, specific and nonspecific of functional systematic approach.

The human body has concentrated all levels of structural organization – from the subcellular to the organismic – arranging them in a certain hierarchy with countless elements and their functions that are beyond comprehension in the cranio-caudal gradient. Therefore, biomedical functional system of any nature and

level must be philosophically comprehended, theoretically constructed and have a specific pragmatic methodology for implementation in the scientific, medical and educational activities.

Controversial to complete opposition experience of intensive care and resuscitation needs a holistic approach to the reanimated person on the basis not only of the three-dimensional nature (spirit, soul and body) [7], but perhaps more challenging – seven-centered (spiritual nature – mind, spirit, absolute spirit and physical nature – the physical body, vital origin, body phantom and passion receptacle) [8], where there is rightly pointed out not only the inner essence of man involved in the formation of consciousness, but also external factors (space, etc.). Therefore the experience assessment on the basis of functional systematic approach will enable us to formulate more precisely the subject and methods of resuscitation from the philosophical point of view taking into consideration the interaction of the human life integrity with death phenomenon as fixed in ontogenesis and will allow to methodically justify the distinguishing of functional systems and standard processes both in sanogenesis and thanatogenesis.

With all kinds of mathematical models there is declared the same principle of their usage: theoretical assignment is formed as mathematical abstraction (model), after that the system is deductively applied to explain certain biomedical phenomena. There occurs obvious deductive a priori realization of the factual material accumulated while the process supervision presented by countless structures and functions of variable elements. The futility of such a realization of functional systematic approach showed the application of mathematical model in the study of brain neurons and other structural and functional units of the central nervous system.

That is why the functional systematic approach should be built on the basis of not only deductive approach, but also on the basis of a specific empirical functional-biochemical material with the following induction, that confirms the necessity of this approach. Along with it mathematical modeling gives way to dialectical thinking and mathematical scheme is estimated as informational noise [9-11].

Mathematical model of a functional system cannot adequately create the form and essence of the positive system function, that is suitable at a certain moment of time and at a certain place, and, as a rule, is already known at the beginning of the real system action, being formed within the system and based on its need for compensation, adaptation and sanogenesis. System-forming factor always determines and goes ahead the actions of its achievement. Therefore, the definition of system-forming factor is the main task in the functional systematic approach.

Many researchers tend to study not the methodology in general, but the methodology of their particular sphere, and often narrower – the methods they

apply in their own research, sinking into pragmatism, simplifying goals and learning objectives, often substituting the philosophy of the systematic approach. Thus, functional systematic approach is identified with a syndrome or a complex, otherwise there is created a system without a system-forming factor, with a positive result.

Search and formation of a backbone factor is a necessary condition for a systematic approach, that identifies both the system itself and the strategy of its usage in any area of study. At the same time the system-forming factor is a transient value or a set of indicators, a dynamic element, especially in medical and biological systems, which often changes its content with the transition of the system to another level of organization and functioning. This very system factor regulates the interaction of many elements in the system that is the essence of self-organization and self-regulation of the system.

Only with the original description of the purpose [12], mathematical modeling of a functional system is possible. The form of the goal in a biomedical system can be represented in two versions: sanogenesis and thanatogenesis. The first option includes compensation and adaptation, and the second – stress and distress.

The goal is formed within the biomedical system itself based on the needs of the whole organism with taking into consideration internal and external factors and their memory. The goal is always ahead of implementation mechanisms. In addition, the uniqueness of biomedical systems is that obtaining useful results is maturing within the system, in the depths of its central and peripheral functional processes and neuro-humoral mechanisms, and implemented in the whole body, affecting both the functions of consciousness and their vegetative supplying.

Excessiveness of the empirical analytical approach to biomedical systems is becoming more dangerous and can "drown" the researchers in the "flood" of disparate facts, whereas excessive theorizing can lead to theory for the sake of theory. In this case, both will be without any result. An example of such a situation may be excessive accumulation in the intensive care expert assessment and prognostic scales (APACHE of different generations (Acute Physiology And Chronic Health Evaluation) W. Knaus et al., 1985, SAPS (Simplified Acute Physiological Score) J. Le Gall et. al., 1984, 1993)), SIRS (systemic inflammatory response syndrome) Bone R. et al., 1992), SOFA (Sepsis-related Organ Failure Assessments Score/Sequential Organ Failure Assessment) Vincent, R. Morreno, J. Takada et. al., 1996) [13] etc., applied in practical work of anaesthetists and resuscitation experts. The set of elements in these scales is not systematized or only united on the basis of combined organ-physiological approach, without specifying the final positive result on the basis of functional systematic approach. Numerous functional-biochemical parameters without backbone factor "blur" a holistic understanding of a critical patient, making it is impossible to implement a

successful resuscitation and rehabilitation. Each organ-physiological system is focused only on a comparison of its own medium statistical physiological indicators, often without hierarchy and functions volatility in a critical state of a patient. Such a situation is aggravated by excessive pragmatism of narrowly specialized professionals involved in all phases of intensive care and resuscitation.

Thus, initially claimed subject matter "resuscitation and intensive care" or "resuscitation" in the form of "management a human body at a critical state" is a very complicated, almost indescribable as a system subject, involving interpretation of resuscitation with a new approach, different from the multiple organ dysfunction syndrome. Huge a priori and empirical data accumulated over the last century of the organ dysfunction study of critical patients, can be the basis of a new original approach, not only in terms of the principal provisions of the functional systematic approach, but also the revival of the nervism theory, undeservedly forgotten in our domestic medicine.

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